

What No One Tells You About Page Pruning in Parquet: The Real Cost of Page Index Parsing

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Abstract

Columnar storage formats, such as Apache Parquet, are the backbone of modern data analytics in the cloud. Over the years, however, the characteristics of data stored in these files have been shifting: wide tables with thousands of columns are common today but were rare at conception. This shift exposes inefficiencies that today's real-world use cases experience, but are not part of the previous scientific related work.

The inefficiency we focus on is how the metadata parsing for page pruning in Parquet works. This becomes unexpectedly expensive for wide tables, as we also show with experiments. To overcome this issue, we propose a new way of encoding using FlatBuffers that reduces access cost by almost an order of magnitude.

Since page-level pruning is an important optimization for avoiding unnecessary data movement in disaggregated architectures, our ongoing work is an enabler both of more efficient distributed systems and also opens research opportunities for offloading pruning to the storage layer.

CCS Concepts

• Information systems → Data Layout; Column Stores; Query optimization.

Keywords

Apache Parquet, Data Pruning, Metadata Encoding, Columnar Formats

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1 Introduction

Columnar formats such as Apache Parquet [1] are central to cloud analytics because they enable high compression, column-at-a-time processing, and efficient predicate evaluation. These formats were designed over a decade ago for storage and workload characteristics of that era. Namely, relatively slow persistent media and OLAP schemas with modest column counts. Modern analytics workloads, however, increasingly use very wide tables, and as table width and fragmentation grow [2, 15, 24], components of Parquet files

Figure 1: Total cost of reading a column with page pruning enabled, normalized to the full column scan time. With Thrift (the default Parquet index encoding), wide tables do not gain performance improvement when selectivity is high, while for FlatBuffers (our proposed encoding), pruning is always beneficial.

that were previously not seen as crucial for high performance are becoming bottlenecks [24].

A concrete example is the overhead of page index parsing used for page pruning. Parquet stores per-page statistics (e.g., min/max values, similar to those at the row group level) that libraries can use to skip irrelevant portions of the file without a full scan. However, due to the cost of parsing the page index¹, pruning can become impractical unless selectivity is both low and reliably predictable. Figure 1 visualizes the relative runtime for reading a column from a Parquet file with page pruning, compared to a full scan. The cost of index-based access can be higher than a full scan already at medium selectivities for wide tables (see Section 2 for more details of the experiment). For tables with 1000 columns, pruning pages is only beneficial if more than $\approx 35\%$ of the pages are pruned, while for 2000 columns the ratio increases to $\approx 45\%$.

We find that the high index parsing cost is due to the serialization format Parquet uses. The current layout favors compactness but forces sequential decoding. We propose to replace the current format with FlatBuffers [6], a serialization format that allows for (1) partial decoding of index metadata, (2) zero-copy deserialization, and (3) exhibits less complex parsing logic. Microbenchmarks in Section 3 show that it reduces index access time by up to an order of

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¹In this work we rely on the parquet-rs Rust library v56 and v57 as baseline for a state of the art Thrift parser deployed in connection with Parquet parsing. The newer version, v57, is our default choice because it has more optimizations and generally outperforms the older one.

Figure 2: Time needed to access the page index metadata (a) and metadata access speedup of FlatBuffers over Thrift, comparing the Thrift-based parser from the parquet-rs Rust library v56 and v57 as baselines (b). Both scale linearly with the page index size, however, the runtime for parsing Thrift-encoded page indices shows a higher linear scaling coefficient than the FlatBuffers-encoded version.

magnitude in representative wide-table scenarios (also see Figure 1). As a result, pruning becomes a safe and predictable optimization for query optimizers, without risking query slowdown.

A hardware-friendly index layout also unlocks novel ways of offloading page pruning to near-data processing elements, which are playing an increasingly important role in modern disaggregated architectures [9, 22, 23]. Prior work has demonstrated the use of ARM cores [4, 7, 8, 11, 12] and FPGAs [10, 13, 14, 17–19, 21] on smart storage devices to offload user-defined functions closer to the data. Our FlatBuffers-based encoding maps more efficiently to processing on constrained execution environments, in contrast to Thrift, which requires sequential deserialization not suited for such hardware. In Section 4, we show that thanks to the new index encoding, an ARM-based smart storage could perform pruning at rates comparable to server CPUs for many workloads.

In summary, this paper shows that index parsing is a growing bottleneck for wide-table analytics in Parquet, and we introduce a flat, hardware-friendly serialization based on FlatBuffers. We can already demonstrate large reductions in overhead, without having to modify the rest of the Parquet files, and our work enables future near-data pruning for smart storage.

2 Apache Parquet and Page Pruning

Apache Parquet is a widely adopted columnar storage format for analytical and ML workloads. It provides multiple levels of data pruning, using metadata statistics at different granularities — from row groups down to individual pages — allowing readers to skip irrelevant data early during a scan. The finest granularity of pruning is at the page level: Parquet stores a page index alongside the data, containing min/max statistics for each page in every column. When a query carries a filter predicate, the reader compares the predicate bounds against these statistics to determine whether a page can be skipped entirely — if the predicate value falls outside a page’s min/max range, that page is guaranteed to contain no matching rows and is never read.

Page-level pruning offers compelling benefits: reduced memory footprint, lower I/O bandwidth consumption, and faster query execution. Despite these potential benefits, page-level pruning does

not appear to be widely used in production systems. This can be attributed to the fact that the effectiveness of pruning does not only depend on index access costs but also on how data is physically ordered within the file. When data is sorted or clustered on the query predicate columns, page-level statistics are highly selective, and pruning skips large portions of the file. When data is stored in random order, the data of interest overlaps across pages and pruning yields less benefit. Since page pruning comes with an additional index access overhead, if the overhead is too large and data is randomly distributed on pages, the cost of pruning may outweigh the benefit of skipping pages. As we explain in the next section, our changes to the index encoding will decrease the overheads significantly and make pruning more practical.

To measure the overhead of index parsing, we compare the time spent parsing page index metadata against the time spent reading actual data pages across a range of table shapes and page selectivities. Each page in the Parquet file stores min/max statistics in the page index; these are used to evaluate the filter predicate and determine which pages to read. We define page selectivity as the fraction of pages in a column that pass this predicate—a selectivity of 0.1 means only 10% of pages are read after pruning. We generate synthetic Parquet files with 60M rows (row group size of 1M), varying column counts from 20 to 2000. These column counts are chosen to represent both traditional workloads—for example, the Lineorder table in SSB [16] has 18 columns—and wide table shapes becoming increasingly common in modern workloads [24]. The experiment ran on a server-grade CPU (AMD Threadripper PRO 3955WX).

Figure 1 shows the total cost of page pruning—metadata parsing plus reading the selected pages, normalized to the cost of a full column scan (expressed as a percentage). A value above 100% means metadata parsing overhead makes pruning slower than a full scan. The Thrift-based results correspond to the page index parser in the parquet-rs Rust library version 57, which serves as our baseline. For narrow tables (20 to 100 columns), the total pruning cost remains below 100% across all selectivities, as metadata parsing is inexpensive enough that it does not impact the total cost. As tables grow wider, a selectivity threshold emerges above which

Figure 3: Replacing Thrift encoding with FlatBuffers enables direct random access to any element in a sequence without the need to deserialize preceding elements. This feature is particularly valuable for column-level filtering as it allows jumping straight to the target column index and skip unnecessary data.

metadata parsing overhead makes pruning slower than simply reading the entire column. This threshold shifts with table width: for a 1000-column table, it falls around 0.65, and for a 2000-column table, it drops further to around 0.55. As tables grow wider, pruning becomes profitable over a narrower range of selectivities, and an incorrect pruning decision results in worse performance than a full scan.

3 New Encoding for Page Index

As shown in Section 2, the Apache Thrift Compact Protocol introduces a significant overhead when parsing page indices, especially in wide tables. This inefficiency is explained by the use case it was designed for: Thrift is designed for RPC applications, where fast serialization speed and small IO footprint is prioritized over fast deserialization. To this end, Thrift’s data schema uses size reducing methods, such as using variable-length encoded integers and packed layout of message structs. Due to this design, data is unaligned and not padded. This inhibits efficient parsing: skipping parts of the metadata is not possible, as the preceding data needs to be decoded to know the position of the succeeding data. In the case of page pruning in Parquet with low page selectivity, offset indices of not selected pages would still need to be parsed.

To address the aforementioned shortcomings of Thrift, we propose to use FlatBuffers instead. FlatBuffers employ fixed-length integers and alignment of data. Alignment of components of a struct is realized using a vtable, which allows for directly jumping to any arbitrary component in constant time. Furthermore, FlatBuffers only uses fixed-length primitive types, which simplifies decoding logic. Figure 3 demonstrates the benefits of using FlatBuffers over Thrift during the page index parsing.

The total cost of page pruning using FlatBuffers encoding is shown in Figure 1 relative to full scan. Unlike Thrift, FlatBuffers remains below 100% across all selectivities and column counts tested. Notably, at a selectivity of 1.0, where all pages are read, FlatBuffers-based pruning remains below the full scan baseline. This is because adopting FlatBuffers for the page index also eliminates the file footer metadata parsing step that Thrift requires, reducing the overhead even when no pages are skipped. This saving becomes more pronounced as tables grow wider, further widening the gap between the two encodings.

Figure 2a shows the absolute metadata parsing time for both FlatBuffers and Thrift as a function of the multiplication of the

Figure 4: Page index parsing time on Bluefield 2 (ARM) and Threadripper (server-class CPU) for FlatBuffers and Thrift. FlatBuffers parsing time is several orders of magnitude lower than Thrift on ARM, demonstrating the feasibility of offloading page index parsing to ARM-based storage controllers.

number of columns and number of rows across three page sizes (128, 512, and 1,024 KB). Both encodings scale linearly with page index size, but with markedly different slopes: Thrift’s slope is steeper than that of FlatBuffers for all data page sizes.

While FlatBuffers offers more efficient (random) access, they occupy more memory compared to Thrift. However, this overhead is negligible in the context of the Parquet file size. In our test dataset, FlatBuffers consistently produces a larger page index than Thrift, as its fixed-width, aligned layout trades compactness for direct field access. However, the difference is small: at 1000 columns, the FlatBuffers page index is approximately 0.057% of the total file size compared to 0.046% for Thrift. Across all configurations, the page index remains well below 0.1% of total file size, making the size overhead of FlatBuffers an acceptable tradeoff for the parsing speedup it delivers.

4 Enabling Offload to the Storage Layer

As an interesting added benefit, the use of FlatBuffers creates opportunities for offloading page index parsing to smart storage devices. The benefit of this offload is that the storage controller, or an FPGA in FPGA-equipped devices, evaluates the page index locally and issues read requests only for the pages that pass the predicate, without transferring the index across the storage interconnect.

A key research question is whether the compute capacity of devices, i.e., modest ARM cores or small FPGAs, is sufficient to parse the page index at a latency comparable to a server-class CPU. To answer this question, we run the FlatBuffers page index parser on NVIDIA Bluefield 2 (8 Cortex-A72 cores@2.5GHz; 16 GBs of RAM@3200MT/s), and compare its access time against a server-class CPU (AMD Threadripper PRO 3955WX). Figure 4 shows this comparison. The results reveal a difference between the two encodings. For Thrift, parsing time grows with column count on both platforms, and Bluefield is consistently 3–4× slower than Threadripper. For FlatBuffers, parsing time is nearly flat across all column counts on both platforms. On Bluefield, the difference between Thrift and FlatBuffers parsing time is particularly striking—at 2000 columns, Thrift takes 1s while FlatBuffers remains below 10⁻⁵s. This confirms that FlatBuffers is not just a performance improvement at

the host, but also in the storage layer, and an enabler of in-storage page index parsing.

We also sketch why FlatBuffer encoding is a better fit for FPGA-based parsing than Thrift: Parsing FlatBuffers involves two phases: an initial pointer-chasing step to locate the relevant list in the page index, followed by sequential access to the list elements themselves, such as page offsets and page sizes. The former step can be costly on FPGAs but represents a small fraction of the parsing cost. The latter step is well-suited for FPGAs. Thanks to fixed-length elements the FPGA can read multiple elements in parallel within a single clock cycle. Thrift, by contrast, uses variable-length encoding for its lists, which requires resource-heavy realignment logic that maps poorly onto hardware pipelines [20]. FlatBuffers' fixed-length list elements eliminate this complexity, resulting in a significantly more efficient FPGA kernel for page index parsing.

5 Related Work

Our findings are reinforced by recent related work: storage systems are moving away from Thrift for storage and Protocol Buffers for communication, to make random access and wide-table projections more efficient. For instance, F3 [25] and Vortex [3] use FlatBuffers to encode metadata to address the shortcomings of conventional serialization schemes with regard to random access. A similar intent motivates a recent extension to the Parquet specification [5], that allows for encoding parts of the metadata using custom methods. This extension should address the shortcomings of the Thrift-based metadata encoding in wide table projections while keeping the file backward-compatible to old Parquet readers. Finally, the recent work on Bullion [15] is another columnar storage system, with the goal to provide an efficient storage system for ML applications. Among the main contributions is the compact metadata layout, which is similar to FlatBuffers [15] and should improve wide-table projections by allowing metadata reads without deserialization.

6 Conclusion

In this work, we propose a modification to Parquet's page index encoding to reduce metadata parsing overhead. Our experiments show that Thrift-encoded page index imposes significant overhead for wide tables, limiting the benefits of page pruning. We demonstrated that substituting Thrift with FlatBuffers keeps page pruning effective across all selectivities. Finally, we compared the runtime of page index parsing on a server CPU and a small ARM CPU, and found that FlatBuffers has additional benefits for execution on low-power embedded cores, opening the door to offloading pruning decisions to the storage layer.

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